

**A STUDY OF NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY (NEP 2020) WITH
REFERENCE TO AUTONOMOUS COLLEGE CURRICULUM
EXPECTED BY THE STUDENT'S FRATERNITY**

Dr. Manasi Atitkar* & Dr. Anil Swami**

* Vice Principal, MIT Arts, Commerce & Science College, Alandi, Pune, Maharashtra

** Assistant Professor, MIT Arts, Commerce & Science College,
Alandi, Pune, Maharashtra

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Abstract:

This Research paper aims at providing skill development courses in the curriculum which is the need of today's era. Autonomy provides freedom of setting the curriculum which makes it very dynamic. Ultimate aim of any education system is to create the meaningful job to the students and make them competent and skilful so that they can stand on one's own feet strongly. Today's Gen'z demands practical approach based on real life examples and its application in today's world. Researcher has made an attempt to throw some light on the requirements of the curriculum expected by the student's fraternity. This study highlights the need for skill-based program in the curriculum to make the students all-rounder and industry ready. Researcher has considered the background of National education Policy 2020 and importance of autonomy in the research paper and followed by the analysis of responses from the students on the curriculum revision.

Key Words: NEP 2020, Autonomy, Skill Development Courses and Competency Building.

Introduction of NEP:

National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) was approved by the Union Cabinet of India on 29th July 2020 to be implemented gradually across India to bring about profound constructive changes in the various aspects of education with an objective to make Indian Education second to none. The rich heritage of ancient and eternal Indian knowledge and thought has been a guiding light for this Policy. The new policy seeks to implement the proposed changes through the facilitators of education viz. boards, universities, schools, colleges and teachers making them dynamic and adapt to the changes in the way they operate and approach education and the teaching learning process. With this regard it is obligatory on the part of an educational institute to have a thorough comprehension of the policy and to work accordingly by following the policy guidelines.

Literature Review:

The policy states that the world is undergoing rapid changes with various dramatic scientific and technological advancements, such as the rise of big data, machine learning, and artificial Intelligence, many jobs are likely to be taken over by machines, while the need for a skilled Workforce, particularly involving mathematics, computer science, and data science, in conjunction with multidisciplinary abilities across the sciences, social sciences, and humanities, will be increasingly in greater demand. With this respect there is a lot of focus on integrated multidisciplinary approach. To shift the focus of education from content to learning about how to think critically and solve problems, how to be creative and multidisciplinary, and how to innovate, adapt, and absorb new material in novel and changing fields. Referred by Sunil Kumar Saroha, & Uttam Anand (2020). New instruction procedure 2020 Highlights: To see huge movements in schools and advanced edification. IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSRJHSS), 25 (8), 59-62.

What does Education Policy mean?

Education policy refers to the collection of laws and rules that govern the operation of education systems.

Why is it Important to Study Education Policy?

Policies are important because they help a school/college to establish rules and procedures and create standards of quality for learning and safety, as well as expectations and accountability. Without education policy, educational institute would lack the structure and unable to meet the needs of students. Education is fundamental for achieving full human potential, developing an equitable and just society and promoting national development. Providing universal access to quality education is the key to economic growth, social justice, equality, scientific advancement, national integration and cultural preservation; and for India's continued ascent, progress, and leadership on the global stage. India will have the highest

youth population in the world over the next decade, and ability to provide high-quality educational opportunities to them will shape the future of the country.

The aim must be for India to have an education system that ensures equitable access to the highest-quality education for all learners regardless of social and economic background. To achieve this, actions must be taken now and with urgency. The gap between the current state of learning outcomes and what is desirable must be bridged through undertaking major reforms to bring the highest quality and integrity into the system. The Union cabinet in July 2020 approved the New Education Policy (NEP), which aims at Universalisation of education from pre-school to secondary level.

Key Features of NEP 2020:

- Universalisation of education from pre-school to secondary level with 100% Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in school education by 2030 and aims to raise GER in higher education to 50 %by 2025
- NEP 2020 will bring two crores out of school children back into the main stream.
- The 10+2 structure of school curricula is to be replaced by a 5+3+3+4 curricular structure.
- It will include 12 years of schooling and 3 years of Anganwadi and pre-schooling.
- NCERT will develop NCFECCE i.e. National Curricular and Pedagogical Framework for Early Childhood Care and Education for children up to the age of 8.
- A National Book Promotion Policy is to be formulated.
- Flexibility in learning.
- Skill advancement.
- Learner’s development.
- New vistas of learning.
- Quality dimensions.

Notable areas under: NEP 2020:

- Multi-Disciplinary Education
- Holistic Development of students
- Flexibility
- Emphasis of Creative and Critical Thinking
- Continuous Assessment
- Role of teacher has changed in to facilitator
- Inclusivity and Synergy in all Curriculums

Institute Autonomy Background:

Autonomy Provides liberty to education system to set the curriculum as per their own need. It allows the institution to create different and unique colour pallet which ultimately turn into distinguished picture. Every institute has their own strength and weakness. Here, Autonomy gives the opportunity to capitalise your strength smartly and overcome the weakness by taking its responsibility. There are four dimensions in any education system where autonomy is implemented aggressively.

Table 1

1) Academic Autonomy

- i) Curriculum
- ii) Teaching methodology
- iii) Evaluation
- iv) Assessment Strategy.

3) Financial Autonomy

- i) Tuition fee.
- ii) budgeting
- iii) Fund raising

2) Administrative Autonomy

- i) Recruitment.
- ii) Admission.
- iii) Campus management.

4) Organisational Autonomy

- i) Independent structure.
- ii) Decision-Making process.
- iv) Organogram.

If any of the educational institute uses autonomy with its fullest capacity it will create wonders in the student’s life. Effective Autonomy will ensure academic excellence, administrative efficiency, up to the mark financial management and automatically it increases the reputation of the institute. In this context researcher has made an attempt to know the requirements of final stakeholder i.e., student about autonomy and upgradation of curriculum in the autonomy. Referred by Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S. (2020). Analysis of the Indian National Education Policy 2020 towards Achieving its Objectives. International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS), 5(2), 19-41.

Research Method and Methodology:

The research paper is based on primary and secondary data. Primary data is collected through the survey-based method. As NEP 2020 is emphasizing on collaboration aspect. It has focused on industry integration, involvement of Industries in the syllabus designing and overall practical skills development of students. Considering this important perspective researcher has designed the research design by collecting first-hand information from Students regarding requirement of upgradation in the syllabus. Survey conducted for 45 Students from various program. Accordingly, the analysis is done and conclusion is drawn. Secondary data is collected through the available data on NEP 2020 from journals, research papers and reports.

Research Analysis:

1. Course wise Classification of the Respondent:

Figure 1

Qualification:

45 responses

Observation:

Above figure shows the Total no of respondant from the various Courses. 55.6% respondents are from B.Sc and M.Sc (CS) students constituting more than half the respondents. B.Sc (regular) and BBA (IB) students were least in the number of respondents. BCA and BBA respondents contributed almost 26 percent of the total respondents. MCA and B.COM students consituted less along with B.Sc (regular) and BBA (IB) respondents. These four have less than 20 percent contribution in the respondent list.

2. Do You Think That Current Syllabus of University Fulfil the Industry Requirement?

Figure 2

44 responses

Observation:

It has been observed that 13.6% of Students responded positively that the Current syllabus of university is suitable and fulfils all the fundamental Requirements of the Industry. On the other hand, 86.4% of students need more changes in the current syllabus as per the industry requirement. So, the highest percentage of respondent feels that the current syllabus of university needs to be changed or more advanced.

3. Do You Think Autonomous Colleges or Universities Provide More Updated Syllabus?

Figure 3

44 responses

Observation

The highest percentage of people around 81.8% of students are convinced that autonomous colleges or universities provide more updated syllabus than Affiliated college where as 18.2% of students are more or less satisfied with the updated syllabus from the Autonomous colleges and universities.

4. Which Domain has More Job Opportunities in IT Industry?

Figure 4

44 responses

Observation:

As per the job opportunities in IT industry majority of Respondents have given their highest priority to the domains like Cloud domain, Artificial intelligence / Machine learning and Big data domain. To the domains like Application development, SAP domain, Network security domain, Testing and automation, web tooling (full stack) and digital marketing have given second priority by the respondent. Other than that marketing, BPO, International Business, Investment banking operation, Cyber security, IOT. Full stack development, IT consulting, Fintech domains are on lowest priority given by the respondent.

5. Would You Like to Include Employability Skill Development Subjects In Syllabus?

Figure 5

44 responses

Observation:

Among the 44 responses 95.5% of students responded that they would like an incorporation of Employability Skills development subjects in Syllabus and very few respondents feels that existing syllabus is more than enough.

6. Which Subjects Would You Like to Include as a Employability Skill Development Subjects in Syllabus?

Figure 6

Observation:

In the above figure respondent have given highest priority to skills like Communication, Leadership, management, skills management, Critical thinking, Emotional intelligence and Collaboration and very few responses were given to the skills like marketing, PORST, Excel, SAP module and finance Management.

Findings & Recommendations:

Every relationship from personal to global rests on the bedrock of trust. Trust is not acquired easily. Growth is accumulated painstakingly through dedication and obsessive commitment of teachers and management. Under the NEP 2020 the role of HEI (Higher Educational Institution) has changed a lot over last decade. Incremental changes have been occurring across fields leading to various new age technologies like augmented reality, virtual reality, brain-computer interface, Artificial intelligence, Block chain technology, and Cloud Computing etc. These technological advancements are revolutionizing higher

education by improving accessibility, personalizing learning experiences and preparing students for this dynamic world. Researchers has developed a 'Wellness Wheel' which is composed of 8 dimensions.

Figure 7

It states the required competencies in today's world. As per the research analysis and objective of NEP 2020 (National Education policy) the Autonomous colleges should build a competency model and make 'Gene's a skilful generation. Researcher has made an attempt to prepare This Wellness Wheel which will suffice the need of today's generation.

- **Academic Competence:** Every attempt in regard to infrastructure should be designed to support academic pursuit. Academic excellence is nurtured by a team of dedicated faculty members who are expert in their domains. Up skilling and strengthening of the curriculum should be distinguished practices of Autonomous College.
- **Global Competence:** Every Autonomous Institute should be actively engaged in establishing collaborations with the international universities. These partnerships offer various opportunities to the students in the format of exchange programs, twinning program and global exposure.
- **Social Competence:** Various social initiatives always encourage students to use their skills for the betterment of society.
- **Physical and Mental Competence:** Competency is built up by exposing the talent of the students through various artistic, creative and physical developmental activities. Different clubs, forums and groups should be formed. Education should not confine between the four walls of classroom. Autonomous Institution should place equal emphasis on holistic development of students through a variety of co-curricular and Extra-curricular activities.
- **Research and Innovation Competence:** Research and Innovation in the college premises should be inseparable arm for the Autonomous Institution. The college should promote research-based activities through various expert talks, Workshops and Competitions. Innovative mind should be also nurtured through the Entrepreneurship development.
- **Professional Competence:** Every HEI now a days cannot work in isolation. Collaboration with industry experts to gain practical exposure is very much essential. We don't have to produce 'Book Worm' but skilful generation which will work in a real-life practical world. Having associations always contribute to cutting edge advancements in their field of study.
- **Emotional and Spiritual Competence:** Emotional health focuses on person's individual feelings, experiences and how they manage them. Emotional competence is a crucial part of wellbeing and affects various areas of our day-to-day life. Feeling of relatedness should be developed among the students by inculcating the feeling that all are one.
- **Technical Competence:** As digitization and sophistication are the faces of new era. Teaching and learning must be integrated with technology. Smart classroom, Digital library, Use of ERP systems should be outcome of autonomous Institution, for developing the technical competence among the students. New age technologies, Block chain technology, AR/VR and AI are revolutionizing the higher education system. Various skill-based certifications and training should be a part of regular curriculum and students should be nurtured with cutting age technology and upbeat knowledge. Referred by National Education Policy 2020, Ministry of Human Resource Development, Govt. of India.

Conclusion:

The educational institutions have to undergo the changes in order to make education more experiential, holistic, integrated, inquiry-driven, discovery-oriented, learner-cantered, discussion based, flexible, and, above all, enjoyable. As per the policy purpose, the education system is to develop good human beings capable of rational thought and action, possessing compassion and empathy, courage and resilience, scientific temper and creative imagination, with ethical moorings and values. As a good educational institute, The Autonomous Institution can contribute to achieve this by creating a safe and stimulating environment where every student irrespective of his/her background feels welcomed and cared for, where a wide range of learning experiences are offered making all infrastructural facilities and appropriate resources conducive for learning. Along with this as per the further guidelines for the institutions, The Autonomous Institution must also work for fruitful integration and coordination with other institutions and Industry for operating at various stages of education.

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